

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

СЛЕДЫ ЭВОЛЮЦИОННОЙ ТЕОРИИ В СОЦИОБИОЛОГИИ, РАСИЗМЕ И ТЕОРИЯХ ЭГОИСТИЧНОГО ГЕНА

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TRACES OF EVOLUTIONARY THEORY IN SOCIOBIOLOGY, RACISM, AND EGOIST GENE THEORIES

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье подробно рассматриваются социобиология, расизм и теория эгоистичного гена, которые усилили роль эволюционной теории в формировании человека. Расизм – это убеждение в том, что человеческие группы обладают различными поведенческими чертами и характеристиками, которые подчёркивают физическую сущность человека, и что одна раса важнее и превосходит другую. В социобиологии анализ пределов и возможностей поведения животных и человека имеет большое значение. При решении современных проблем большое значение придаётся принципам теории Дарвина, включая естественный отбор. В теории эгоистичного гена гены описываются как машины и, как предполагается, управляют людьми.

ABSTRACT

This article examines in detail sociobiology, racism, and the selfish gene theory, which have enhanced the importance of evolutionary theory in the formation of man. Racism is the belief that human groups have distinct behavioral traits and characteristics that emphasize physical appearance and that one race is more important and superior than another. In sociobiology, the analysis of the limits and possibilities of animal and human behavior is of great importance. In solving current problems, the principles of Darwin's theory, including natural selection, are given great importance. In the selfish gene theory, genes are described as machines and are assumed to control humans.

Ключевые слова: эволюция, естественный отбор, социобиология, расизм, эгоистичный ген, поведение.

Keywords: evolution, natural selection, sociobiology, racism, selfish gene, behavior.

The doctrine of “sociobiology”. One of the main doctrines that seeks to biologize the essence of man is the doctrine of “sociobiology”. The main representatives of the doctrine of sociobiology, which is currently widespread in the West, are M. Reuse, M. Midgme, E. Wilson and others. Sociobiology is known as the subject of E.O. Wilson’s work “Sociobiology: A New Synthesis” (1975). In this book, he carried out a “systematic study of the biological basis of all social behavior” by studying social behavior. In explaining the “biological basis of behavior”, Wilson refers to the social and ecological causes that drive the evolution of behavior in animal populations, rather than the neurological or psychological causes of behavior in individuals. Wilson clearly understood that sociobiology and neuroscience have important theoretical interactions.

The famous American scientist E. Wilson, known as one of the creators of this doctrine, suggested that in order to compile a list of animals on Earth, it is necessary to look at human history from the perspective of a zoologist from another planet. With this approach, all the humanities and social sciences are perceived as separate specializations of biological science. In his opinion, history and literature are considered only as meth-

ods of studying the behavior of a person who is considered a biological species. Wilson commented on the theoretical foundations of this doctrine in his book “Sociobiology: A New Synthesis”, published in 1975. Wilson stated that our main goal is to approach morality, determinism, egoism, aggression, freedom, altruism and other human characteristics in a new way and direction. In realizing this goal, Wilson attached special importance to the analysis of the limits and possibilities of animal and human behavior. In solving the problems we are considering, great importance is given to the principles of Darwinian theory, including natural selection. The most important point is that the results obtained on animals were applied to human behavior. Thus, Wilson very unreasonably attributed anthropology to biology, and biology to molecular genetics [3].

Critics have argued that “Pop Sociobiologists” are committed to a form of genetic determinism, overly strong adaptation, and tend to ignore the effects of learning and culture. The term sociobiology is sometimes used to refer to approaches to human behavior that retain the behavioral focus that Wilson refers to [9].

Wilson showed that social behavior in living organisms has a biological basis. He understood them as the biological principles on which life is built in any

animal community, including humans, and, in his opinion, this was the result of evolution. Wilson argued that only 10% of human behavior is genetically determined, the rest is related to the environment. The thesis that a person's obedience to biological laws in his actions affects his aggressiveness, sexuality, and ethics is not unanimously accepted by scientists in various fields of science. However, Wilson noted that ultimately it was sociobiology and evolution that provided the principles for explaining the social behavior of animals, including humans. He argued that all animal behavior, including humans, is a product of heredity, environmental stimuli, and the past. Wilson continued to develop Darwin's theory of evolution, applying evolution not only to individual organisms, but to the entire living world, including humans.

In general, sociobiologists believe that "the theory of coevolution of genes and culture completely changes the ideas about the nature and origin of man. This theory claims that in man the processes of genetic and cultural evolution occur simultaneously. They are interconnected" [3]. However, when approaching the problem from this position, genes play the leading role. According to sociobiologists, genes are the ultimate cause of many human actions. Therefore, man is perceived as an object of biological knowledge. Wilson saw the main goal of sociobiology in studying the biological foundations of all forms of social behavior in animals, including humans. The main idea of this concept is this: there is no serious trait in man beyond his biological nature. According to representatives of sociobiologists, most likely, a person's moral feelings are also transmitted by inheritance through biological channels. As an example, sociobiologists cited the absence of marriage between blood relatives in primitive society. In their opinion, this prohibition came to human society from the animal kingdom. Sociobiologists also considered aggression to be an important and integral feature of man. According to sociobiologists, human intelligence is also the most important tool intended for biological reproduction. This concept interpreted man from a naturalistic position. According to Wilson, there is no boundary between animals and humans. This is explained by the fact that all living beings live according to the same principles. Many phenomena and actions that we consider to be the achievements of human civilization are also present in the behavior of animals. For example, we can note that wolves live in packs, bees in families, and gazelles in groups. According to sociobiologists, these forms of association are considered the first harbingers of social life. Also, according to them, altruism is not a specific human phenomenon, but a property of all living organisms.

According to Wilson, the subject of sociobiology is "the study of the biological basis of social behavior. Wilson based his analysis of this or that aspect of human behavior on the assumption that, like animals, humans behave in a way that is similar to that of animals, and that the evolutionary laws established for animal species apply equally to human populations. Wilson wrote in this regard: "Let us move away from conventionality and view man as a part of nature, and as if we

were ethologists from another planet compiling a catalog of the social species of the Earth. In such a macroscopic approach, the humanities and social sciences would become, at best, branches of biology. The history and fiction of countries and individuals will become the documented ethology of man, and anthropology and sociology will merge to create the sociobiology of one of the primate species" [9]. To substantiate his extremely superficial concept, E. Wilson refers to common features in the behavioral characteristics of humans and primates, children and young people, to individual rules of interaction between relatives, to the strength of parent-child relationships, and so on. From this, Wilson concludes that the main types of human social behavior, including the determining role of the male sex in establishing social relations, territorial aspects of behavior, and rules of kinship relations, arise as phenotypes subject to biological evolution.

In his early works, Wilson emphasized the need to actively connect biological knowledge with the study of human nature. But the whole point was that the very concept of "human nature" was extremely vague [9]. Therefore, Wilson set as the main task the study of either the natural and biological foundations of human life, or its essence. Wilson directly wrote that *Homo sapiens* is an ordinary animal species with genetically diverse behavior [10]. He was also confident that we would soon be able to identify most of the genes that determine behavior. At the same time, Wilson noted the influence of cultural factors, training and upbringing on human development.

Wilson proposed reconstructing the "previous evolutionary history of social organization" in order to study and understand man more deeply. At the same time, a very specific situation was put forward: to trace similarities in the behavior of humans and other animals. Sociobiologists argue that since many social sciences study humans, biological disciplines should be in close contact with them. Wilson notes that, unfortunately, biology is perceived as an "anti-discipline" in relation to social sciences such as philosophy, psychology, anthropology, sociology, and economics. In his opinion, this situation should be eliminated.

Compared to traditional biology, sociobiology, as Wilson's supporters believe, has a number of advantages:

1. First of all, sociobiology is a certain body of knowledge formed on the basis of population genetics, evolutionary theory, ethology and ecology. It is, so to speak, a hybrid of disciplines.

2. On the other hand, unlike traditional biological disciplines, sociobiology focuses on social sciences and is able to generate hypotheses that will create a need for fundamentally new types of data in social sciences. Without sociobiology, this need could not have arisen.

3. Finally, according to supporters of sociobiology, it is necessary to actively include biological knowledge in social sciences, primarily knowledge about biological phenomena that are least subject to cultural adaptations [9].

Wilson's primary goal was to make biology the basis of social knowledge. Just as modern neuroscience attempts to explain the physiological basis of thought,

sociobiology must make it its task to reconstruct the evolutionary history of human nature.

Finally, it should be noted that Wilson was the first to attempt to explain the origin of animal and human behavior in an evolutionary way. He claimed that all animal behavior had a biological basis. Trying to justify this error with biological evolution, Wilson assumed that there were specific genes that controlled animal and human behavior. In his book "Human Nature" published in 1978, Wilson extensively discussed many hypotheses about the existence of genes responsible for human behavior, such as hatred, aggression, fear of others, conformity, homosexuality, and characteristic differences between men and women [10].

Another unscientific claim of Wilson's was that living things were merely vehicles responsible for carrying genes, and that their most important and essential function was to carry these genes and pass them on to future generations. According to Wilson's unscientific views, evolution was simply the evolution of genes, natural selection selected genes, and therefore, genes were what seemed most important and necessary. Wilson justified his opinion as follows: "When we approach the issue in a Darwinian sense, we can note that a living being does not live for itself. Its basic function is not to reproduce other living beings, but only to reproduce genes and serve as a carrier of genes. Each living being that arises through sexual reproduction is a special and random subset of the genes that make up that species [11].

The claims put forward by Wilson never went beyond being hypotheses. The ideas of Wilson and his followers remained ideas that could not be explained on the basis of scientific facts. Although it was emphasized that this doctrine had no scientific basis, this doctrine still retains its importance today. The evolutionary hypotheses about human behavior that began with Wilson have now been developed to the most incredible extent through the efforts of many scientists.

Racism theory. Racism or racism theory is one of the most important and fundamental theories in the modern world. Racism is the belief that human groups have different behavioral characteristics and traits based on their physical appearance and that one race is more important and superior than another. It can mean prejudice, hostile and cruel treatment, discrimination or hostility directed against other people because of their different racial or ethnic origin.

When defining racism, we should also note that in the modern sense, this theory often includes the social perception of biological differences between peoples. These ideas can take the form of political systems, social and political actions, practices and beliefs that emphasize the superiority or inferiority of different races, often based on alleged common hereditary traits, qualities and abilities [5].

Since the 19th century, many sciences have supported the idea of dividing human groups into races. Racial characteristics provided the basis for classifying people into races, and it was claimed that the race to which people were born was the basis for their development. Even people's abilities, rights, and privileges were determined by race. Often, studies on the human

genome emphasize that race is of little importance in determining the genetic classification of people, citing a lack of evidence and facts.

Although laws have been passed in many countries of the world to prevent racial traits from causing discrimination between people, these traits cannot be completely prevented even today. In many countries of the world, this theory has reached its peak. Racial discrimination between people has even caused them to have hostile attitudes towards each other. However, if we look at this issue again at the international level, we can see that people who differ in skin color, facial structure, and body size have also begun to be highly valued in the political sphere. In philosophy and other humanities, "race" acts as a form of social structure. In this sense, we can note that although the concepts of race and racism are based on biological qualities, the role of cultural ideology is also very large here. Racism, as an ideological concept, exists in society in both individual and institutional forms. In sociology and social psychology, racial identity is explained from the position of racial identity. Racial identity and the acquisition of this identity are characterized as concepts that often change in research. According to sociologists, racism in modern Western societies has become a more subtle expression of overt racial prejudice. In the humanities, racial discrimination refers to discrimination against someone on the basis of race.

The elimination of rigid racial differences in human ancestry gave rise to scientific racism. Representatives of scientific racism argued that humans were a single species, divided by a common origin. Races were recognized as part of humanity, and all races demonstrated close similarities between people. According to human genome research, it has been emphasized that racial groups do not have a clear genetic basis to date [4].

Racism changes over time and its scope varies from time to time. Racism encompasses all policies, ideologies, rules and laws, and barriers that prevent people from living with justice, dignity, and equality based on their racial identity. This includes harassment, abuse, and humiliation, violence, and intimidating behavior. Racism is considered a dirty theory. Because it divides and classifies people based on where they come from and the color of their skin.

Racism occurs in various ways:

- 1) Making jokes and making negative comments about people.
- 2) Calling people racist names and verbally abusing them.
- 3) Displaying racist graphics in public places.
- 4) Exclusion from groups because they are different.
- 5) Being physically abused because of their race [6].

Racism generally involves negative emotional reactions to people or groups, the acceptance of negative stereotypes, and racial discrimination against individuals, which in some cases leads to violence. Discrimination refers to the differential treatment of members of different ethnic, religious, national, or other groups. Discrimination is usually a behavioral manifestation of

prejudice and involves negative, hostile, and harmful treatment of members of rejected groups.

Finally, it should be noted that when talking about the role of biological factors, it is impossible to bypass the theory of racism. This is because this theory reveals a very sad situation in the modern world. People are distinguished from each other based on their physical and physiological characteristics and are subjected to racial discrimination. Although many measures have been taken in this regard, the solution to this problem has only been partial. There is much to be done in this aspect and it is one of the most important issues to be solved in the modern world.

Selfish gene theory. Richard Dawkins is one of the world's most famous evolutionists and one of the greatest proponents of Darwin's theory. According to Dawkins, the most important and significant goal of living beings is to survive, reproduce, and preserve their genes and pass them on to the next generation. According to Dawkins's absurd claim, humans are "robots that preserve genes." Humans' purpose in the world is to multiply the genes they possess and possess, to protect their genes in competition with other genes, and to pass them on to the next generation. According to this materialistic idea, which has not been scientifically proven, if a person's main goal and duty is simply to ensure the continuity of their genes, then there can be no moral criteria for humans. A person should be as selfish and ruthless as possible for the benefit of their own genes. According to this theory, which is a product of Dawkins's irrational ideas, humans themselves are selfish because the genes they possess are selfish.

However, the selfish gene claim is illogical and absurd. Because selfishness is a characteristic of character, and character is a characteristic of the human soul or psyche. Dawkins and many other evolutionists explain genes as if they were beings with consciousness and will. However, according to them, genes are elements of long DNA chains. DNA consists of long nucleotide acid chains attached to each other by phosphate and sugar, that is, they are long molecules. They showed as an example that DNA is considered a molecule in the same way that water (H₂O) or sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) are considered molecules. According to critics of this teaching, the concept of a "selfish gene" is just as meaningless as the concepts of "selfish water", "selfish salt" or "jealous sulfuric acid".

Dawkins and other evolutionists try to present man as a mass of matter, and they want to present any part of this mass of matter as conscious. The claim that genes are conscious is very instructive in terms of assessing the current state of the theory of evolution.

Richard Dawkins wrote the work "The Selfish Gene" in 1976. In his first popular scientific work, the scientist discussed the evolution of species from the point of view of genetics. In this work, Dawkins first introduced the term "meme", and later the word "memetics" was formed in connection with this concept [7]. Memetics is a theory that considers the evolution of culture by analogy with Darwin's biological theory. Dawkins' main idea is that man and all living beings on the planet are mortal machines, the meaning of their individual life is precisely the transfer of genes. From this

it can be concluded that all human life and activity is subordinate to this task. What exactly happens to the "mortal machine" is not so important for genes. Dawkins notes that the selfish gene lives in a world of great competition, deception and exploitation. Also, the altruistic acts that a person can observe in nature do not contradict the basic law of the selfish gene. Dawkins notes that the gene is not only selfish, but also cunning. He consistently defended this idea. In his opinion, only man, the only creature on the planet, was able to organize a rebellion against the intentions of the gene. Culture, according to evolutionists, is the most important level of human development, thanks to which we are not just forms of reproduction and transmission of the gene pool.

In his work "The Selfish Gene", R. Dawkins laid the foundation for a new scientific direction – "memetics". The term "meme" is used to refer to a cultural unit. According to Dawkins' claims, memes reproduce, are transmitted from person to person, undergo changes in society, and thus completely change society [7].

One of the main ideas presented by Dawkins is that the basic elementary particle of all living organisms is not the cell, but the gene that controls the cell. Humans and animals, according to the scientist, are simply survival machines for genes.

Dawkins' theory of "selfish gene" popularizes the gene-centric view of evolution, introduces the concept of "meme", which means a cultural unit that can be copied by one person and transmitted to another [7].

Critics complained to Richard Dawkins that this theory is fatal, that much in our lives is determined even before birth, and how a person will develop, how all this is determined at the genetic level. Trying to substantiate the opinions of critics, Dawkins shows that there are such tendencies in a person that are given to us from birth, but we, people, can change them. Only people are capable of this change. The only creature that can fight the tyranny of selfish replicators under the influence of society, upbringing, education is a person. Dawkins expresses his idea figuratively as follows: "Genes are not strings in the hands of a puppeteer, with which he controls his puppets" [2]. According to Dawkins, genes only control protein synthesis in the cell. In his opinion, during the evolution of genes, a developed brain was formed that could adapt to environmental conditions, assess the situation, model and make independent decisions. Genes, however, can only give general recommendations on what to do. In general, the scientist does not deny that all organisms are dependent on genetics. He emphasizes that culture and education play an important role in this process. In his opinion, a person himself can soften the "selfish gene."

As one of the greatest followers of Darwinism, R. Dawkins notes that the main feature of each individual is selfishness. This is closely related to the process of evolution and natural selection, in which the strong always win over the weak. Weakened individuals, in his opinion, never survive. Dawkins claims that nothing has changed in our modern world.

By "gene", Dawkins means a genetic unit that is small enough to last for many generations and is distributed in many copies [1]. A gene is transmitted from

grandfather or grandmother to grandson, remains unchanged and passes through the intermediate generation without mixing with other genes. In his opinion, if genes were constantly approaching each other, natural selection as we understand it today would be impossible. Another feature of the gene structure is that it never becomes obsolete; it is equally likely to die at the age of a million or a hundred. From a genetic perspective, individuals and groups do not remain fixed during evolution. According to Dawkins, the gene is the basic unit of selfishness.

Genes work by regulating protein synthesis. One way that genes solve the problem of prediction when environmental conditions are sufficiently unpredictable is to equip themselves with a survival machine. Natural selection favors genes that control survival machines so that they can make the best use of the environment.

In each individual, the selfish gene tends to become more and more abundant in a given gene pool. In principle, it does this by helping to program the organs in which it is located for survival and reproduction. According to Dawkins, most genes have more than one phenotypic effect (for example, green eyes or curly hair). Natural selection favors some genes over others not because of the nature of the genes themselves, but because of their consequences, that is, their phenotypic effects.

One of the novel aspects of Dawkins' theory is the replicators. In his view, the selfish gene is an extended phenotype. According to Dawkins, this idea can be applied to living things anywhere in the universe. The basic unit and main engine of life is precisely the replicator. Any object in the universe that makes copies of itself can be called a replicator. Replicators often arise by chance. They can create an infinite number of copies of themselves.

Dawkins encourages us to understand what our genes are trying to do. In this case, he says, we will have a chance to thwart their intentions. No other living being, human, is capable of this. According to him, the reason for this is that humans are the only living being dominated by culture. Those who are very sympathetic to this believe that the influence of genes can be ignored. In any case, according to Dawkins, genes determine behavior only in a statistical sense.

Dawkins notes that there are four types of nucleotide building blocks: A, T, C and G. They are the same in all organisms. However, at the same time, their sequence is different for everyone (identical twins are an exception). DNA is found in every cell and is considered the "blueprint" of the human body. Genes regulate the structure of organisms, but this influence is one-sided: acquired traits are not inherited, each generation starts from scratch.

Genes cannot look ahead or predict. According to Dawkins, they simply exist. At the same time, genes have made great progress in the technology of creating survival machines. Examples of their activity include

the heart, muscles, and eyes. The survival machine contains not one, but thousands of genes. The creation of an organism is a cooperative process in which it is almost impossible to separate the influence of one gene from another. According to Dawkins, the gene is a highly accurate replicator.

Summarizing all that has been said, we can say that the theory of the "selfish gene", which is considered a logical continuation of the theory of biological evolution and the teaching of sociobiology, which accepts the role of genetic factors in humans, is distinguished by its originality. The theory of the selfish gene is considered a more developed form of the teaching of sociobiology. It is claimed that Richard Dawkins' ideas do not coincide with scientific facts, like Edward Wilson's ideas. Nevertheless, this theory also had great supporters. Richard Dawkins extensively substantiates the theory of evolution in his theory and even develops this theory further with new concepts. The selfish gene theory is considered Darwin's theory due to its style. This theory gained popularity by presenting the ideas of neo-Darwinism in an even new way. If we are trying to substantiate the role of genetic factors in humans, we cannot ignore this theory of Dawkins.

R. Dawkins's services in substantiating the role of genetic determinism in modern times are great. The "selfish gene" theory is one of the modern approaches to the problem of evolution [8]. Dawkins' theory opened the way to a new stage in substantiating the genetic deterministic approach in connection with the study of the biological foundations of behavior and its role in natural selection. This path paved the way for the further development of Darwin's theory of evolution in modern times.

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